

A REVIEW: MEMBRANE DISTILLATION FOR ETHANOL SEPARATION FROM FERMENTATION BROTH

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ABSTRACT

Fermentation of biomass is a well known technique used to produce the ethanol that can be used as an energy source to fulfill the energy demand of the rapidly expanding population and fuel demand of the transportation sector. Continuous ethanol separation from the fermentation broths can enhance the efficiency of the fermentation process. Membrane distillation in combination with the fermentation process may be the effective technique for ethanol separation.

Membrane distillation is a separation process in which liquid mixture is vaporized by providing heat and vapour molecules are transferred through the microporous membrane. The required driving force for the Membrane distillation is vapour pressure difference across the microporous membrane which is induced by the temperature difference. Membrane distillation is commercialized for various applications such as desalination, wastewater treatment and in the food industry. This process is also applicable for various fields like Crystallization, treatment of dye effluents, Arsenic removal from aqueous solution and contaminated groundwater, Recovery of aroma compounds, Separation of azeotropic mixture.

This review emphasized on various Membrane distillation configurations, membranes used in membrane distillation, their characteristics and performance parameters for ethanol separation from fermentation broth.

Keywords: Membrane Distillation, Fermentation, Membrane Modules, Ethanol Separation, Membrane Performance.

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1. Introduction: Day to day the demand for energy is increasing rapidly due to modern lifestyle and rapidly expanding human population. Fossil fuel fulfilling the demand of energy will be exhausted in the future. Therefore, alternative energy sources are always on demand (Selvaraj & Banat, 2019). Recently many countries are focusing on bioethanol as an alternative energy source and gasoline replacement or additive (Dias et al., 2009). In the India 98% of the fuel requirement in the road transportation sector is currently met by fossil fuels and the remaining 2% by biofuels and according to the National Policy on Biofuels – 2018, provides an indicative target of 20% ethanol blending under the Ethanol Blended Petrol (EBP) Programme by 2030 (Sarwal et al., 2021). Mainly Ethanol as a biofuel produced by fermentation of sugars by yeasts. The fermentation of the biomass like grains, starches, sugar cellulose etc. are used to produce the alcohol. Ethanol is produced by the fermentation of sugar mostly xylose (C5) and glucose (C6) sugars (mostly xylose and glucose) using classical or GMO yeast strains such as *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (FAQs_on_1G_Bio-Ethanol-converted, 2021). The fermentation reaction is:

sugar + nutrients (cells as catalyst) → ethanol + cells + by-products

Above reaction shows that sugar present in the biomass decomposes into ethanol and carbon dioxide (Gryta et al., 2000). During fermentation, increase in product concentration hampers the microbial activity by product inhibition hence it is important to continuously remove the ethanol from fermented broths. In the earlier year vacuum fermentation and extractive fermentation was used to remove the alcohol from the fermented broths. Since the last few years many researchers have been trying to enhance the application of membranes in this field (Gryta, 2013).

Pervaporation and membrane distillation are promising techniques for alcohol separation. In Pervaporation preferentially ethanol is allowed to pass mostly through the dense membrane hence many researchers emphasize on preparation of ethanol selective membrane with high flux (Banat & Simandl, 1999). In comparison with the pervaporation process membrane distillation required microporous hydrophobic membrane because of this advantage researchers showing their interest to improve the application of membrane distillation for the ethanol separation from fermentation broths.

The performance of membrane distillation depends on porous size of membrane, membrane wettability by the process liquid, capillary condensation inside the pores, partial pressure gradient in the vapour phase, and thickness of the membrane (Smolders & Franken, 1989).

2. Membrane Distillation: Membrane distillation is thermally driven liquid-liquid separation process in which the vapor molecule is transferred through the microporous membrane due to vapor pressure difference across the membrane by the temperature difference (Alkudhiri et al., 2012). Membrane distillation is widely used for the water treatment, desalination, binary mixture separation, and separation of volatile components from multi components mixture (Drioli and Wu, 1985, Andersson et al., 1985 & Nassif et al., 2022). Membrane distillation can be applied for various operations like Crystallization, treatment of dye effluents, Arsenic removal from aqueous solution and contaminated groundwater, Recovery of aroma compounds, Separation of azeotropic mixture (Sparenberg et al., 2022, Fortunato et al., 2021, Manna et al., 2010,

Bagger-Jørgensen et al., 2011, Saurabh Kumar et al., 2013, Kujawa et al., 2015 & Gostoli and Sarti, 1989).

3. MD Configurations: Four Membrane distillation configurations is widely used by the researchers for various separation applications: Direct Contact Membrane Distillation (DCMD), Vacuum Membrane Distillation (VMD), Air Gap Membrane Distillation (AGMD), and Sweeping Gas Membrane Distillation (SGMD)

3.1 DCMD: In direct contact membrane distillation the feed solution and the permeate solution is circulated tangentially to the membrane surface. ensure that the permeate solution is maintained in direct contact with the permeate side of the membrane. The transmembrane temperature difference induces the vapour pressure difference between the both sides of the membrane. One of the molecules of the hot feed solution is evaporated at the liquid/vapour interface, diffuses through the microporous membrane pores and condenses on the permeate side of the membrane (Macedonio, 2015). Pressure difference and permeate flux can be represented by simple correlations:

$$\Delta P = P_{fm} - P_{pm} \dots\dots\dots \text{eq 1}$$

$$N = C(P_{fm} - P_{pm}) \dots\dots\dots \text{eq 2}$$

where ΔP is the vapour pressure difference across the membrane, P_{fm} is the vapour pressure at feed side, P_{pm} is vapour pressure at the permeate side, N is the permeate flux and C is the membrane characteristic parameter (Macedonio, 2015).

Fig. 1. Scheme of the experimental apparatus. 1, bioreactor; 2, thermostat; 3, MD module; 4, pump; 5, distillate tank; 6, heat exchanger; 7, valve 1; and 8, valve 2. T, temperature; D, distillate; F, feed; and B, broth

(Gryta et al., 2000)

Gryta et al. (2000) studied the Ethanol production in membrane distillation bioreactor as shown in Fig 1. The porous capillary polypropylene membrane (nominal and maximum diameter of 0.22 and 0.6 mm, respectively, and a porosity of ca. 73%) were used for the separation of volatile compounds. The feed (fermented broth) flows inside the membranes and The distillate side of MD was filled initially with distilled water and The permeate flux (ethanol + water vapor) transported through the membrane was determined by the measurement of an increase of distillate volume and calculated by following equation:

$$N = \frac{V_D^2 - V_D^1}{At} * 24 \text{ (dm}^3/\text{m}^2 \text{ 24h)} \dots\dots\dots \text{eq 3}$$

where: V_D^2 is the volume of liquid in the MD system on the distillate side, at the start of MD process in dm^3 , V_D^1 is the volume of liquid in the MD system on the distillate side, at the end of MD process, in dm^3 , A is the area of membranes in m^2 , and t is the number of working hours of the MD process in h. The efficiency of conversion of sucrose to ethanol was found to be 0.47–0.51 (g EtOH)/(g of sugar) for the fermentation carried out with the MD system, whereas without MD it was 0.35–0.45 (g EtOH)/(g of sugar).

In another study, extractive fermentation of ethanol using membrane distillation, Udriot et al. (1989) carried out the experiment on laboratory bioreactor linked with MD for the separation of ethanol from the culture medium using A hydrophobic microporous membrane PTFE membrane (mean pore diameter $0.2\mu\text{m}$, porosity 75% and film thickness $120\mu\text{m}$, during laboratory experiment absorbed that membrane wettability, liquid entry pressure (LEP) and membrane pore size playing important role in ethanol separation.

3.2 AGMD: In Air gap membrane distillation stagnant air gas is created between membrane and condensing wall at the permeate side of the membrane. vapour allows it to pass through the membrane pore and Air gap and condensed in the condensing wall surface (Reza & Rahimpour, 2020).

Gostoli and Sarti (1989) carried out the experiment on separation of ethanol from aqueous solution using PTFE membrane of pore size of $0.2\mu\text{m}$, thickness is $60\mu\text{m}$ and porosity 60%. They selected the Air gap membrane distillation [Fig. 2] to avoid the possibility of losing hydrophobicity on the permeate side. They observed that the separation factor increases with the bulk temperature difference as well as with the average temperature and decreases with increasing ethanol concentration in feed. They also pointed out that in direct contact membrane distillation temperature differences across the membrane are quite small because of the liquid phase present in the permeate side. Also observed that in AGMD no change in separation factor with increasing the thickness of air gap at fixed temperature difference but the separation factor changes with increasing air gap thickness when temperature difference between the evaporation and condensation surfaces changes.

Fig. 2. Apparatus employed for air gap membrane distillation; (WB) warm bath; (CB) cold bath; (Th) thermocouples (Gostoli and Sarti, 1989)

3.3 VMD: In vacuum membrane distillation the hot feed is flowing over the membrane and vacuum is applied at the permeate side using vacuum pump, heat loss and mass transfer resistance are reduced due to vacuum. In this module vacuum pressure should be lower than the saturation vapour pressure of the component needs to separate from the hot feed mixture driving force is created across the membrane and the volatile components vapour sucked out from the membrane pore to the permeate side of the membrane get condensed by applying external condenser (Reza & Rahimpour, 2020). Because of vacuum from the permeate side probability membrane may lose their hydrophobicity (Baghel et al., 2017).

Fig 3. Schematic Representation of the Laboratory-Scale Vacuum Membrane Distillation Apparatus

(Zarraa et al. 2024)

Zarraa et al. (2024) studied the influence of various parameters like feed flow rate, initial ethanol concentration, and temperature on the performance of the vacuum membrane distillation as shown in Fig. 3. They casted the polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) membrane by solution casting method and characterized by Scanning Electron Microscopy to study the morphology. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) to determine the functional groups and the possible molecular bonds between chemical compounds, Contact Angle to identify the membrane surface's hydrophilicity and wettability, Membrane Porosity and Pore size. The analysis result shows that the average pore size of the membrane was $0.22 \mu\text{m}$, the contact angle between the PVDF membrane and water drop phase was equal to (110°) , and porosity of membrane was equivalent to 45.6%. They also observed that, the ethanol flux and total permeate flux were increases with increasing initial concentration of ethanol and temperature while the separation factor was decreases.

3.4 SGMD: Sweeping Gas Membrane Distillation The hot fluid is flowing over the membrane and cold inert sweep gas is blowing through the permeate side of the membrane. Vapour molecules permeated through the membrane swept with sweep gas and vapour molecules condensed by the external condenser (Reza & Rahimpour, 2020). In this module the temperature of the sweep gas decreases along the length of the membrane hence driving force may be reduced. To minimize the sweep gas temperature external condensation system may be applicable hence operational cost of the system may be increased (Baghel et al., 2017).

Fig 4. The general scheme of the experimental set-up (Mohammad et al., 2015)

Mohammad et al. (2015) carried out the experiment to investigate the effect of various operating parameters (feed concentration, feed temperature, feed flow rate, and sweeping gas flow rate) on the permeation flux and selectivity of ethanol/water. Commercial flat sheet PTFE membrane of $0.22\mu\text{m}$ pore size has been used to study the application of the sweeping gas membrane distillation process (SGMD) for direct separation of ethanol-water. Investigated that, higher the feed flow rate and feed temperature higher will be the permeation rate. Also investigated that at lower feed temperature permeation flux increases with increasing in the sweeping gas flow rate and selectivity decreases with increase in sweeping gas flow rate for all feed temperatures.

4. Polymeric membranes for MD: Membranes required for the membrane distillation process should be microporous, hydrophobic, chemically inert with good thermal and mechanical properties. Generally for ethanol water separation, membranes are prepared by using hydrophobic polymeric materials like Poly(tetrafluoroethylene) (PTFE), Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF), Polypropylene (PP) etc. (Parani & Oluwafemi, 2021)

Poly(tetrafluoroethylene) PTFE is a high crystalline polymer with high chemical and thermal stability and less flexible because of their high glass transition temperature (T_g) around 126°C . Excellent solvent resistance, low surface adhesion with low surface energy and contact angle of a smooth PTFE surface is about 108°C (Kwong et al., 2007). PTFE is highly hydrophobic because of fluorinated polymers (Drioli & Macedonio, 2015). Fabrication of PTFE membranes is very difficult and costly (Khayet, 2011).

Polypropylene (PP) is a linear hydrocarbon, semi-crystalline, amorphous polymer having T_g -10°C , melting temperature (T_m) $151-166^\circ\text{C}$ and thermal decomposition temperature around 240°C hence good thermal & mechanical properties and good chemical stability. PP is insoluble in many solvents but soluble in 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene, decalin, halogenated hydrocarbons, aliphatic ketones, xylene at relatively high temperature (above 80°C) (Himma et al., 2016). PVDF is a semi crystalline polymer, high mechanical strength, good chemical resistance and thermal stability, PVDF is soluble in some common solvents like N-dimethylacetamide (DMAc), dimethylformamide (DMF) and N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) (Kang & Cao, 2014).

PVDF dissolves in any solvent at room temperature because of this advantage fabrication of this membrane is very easy as compared to PTFE and PP (Khayet, 2011).

5. Membrane Preparation Methods:

5.1 Sintering-extrusion or melt-extrusion Method: PTFE and PP membrane is usually fabricated by the sintering-extrusion or melt-extrusion process. Both the methods are solvent free and very complicated. In the sintering process PTFE resin is mixed with lubricant to form a paste and the paste is extruded into a flat sheet or hollow fiber after that stretching process is applied to form a porous PTFE hollow fibre. Finally, the PTFE hollow fibre membrane is obtained after a heat treatment (Jia et al., 2017; Chopra, 2015; Zhu et al., 2013 & Feng et al., 2017).

Fig 5. Schematic diagram of PTFE membrane preparation process: (a) mixing and aging, (b) preforming, (c) extrusion, (d) stretching and (e) sintering. PTFE: polytetrafluoroethylene (Jia et al., 2017)

In the melt-extrusion method the PTFE is melted by heating and PTFE film is formed by extrusion and stretching. After the annealing and cooling process uniform microporous structure membrane is formed with a pore size in the range of 0.2–20 μm (Chopra, 2015). Zhu et al. (2013) fabricated the Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) hydrophobic hollow fiber membranes using cold pressing method including paste extrusion, stretching and sintering to study the effect of stretching ratio on the characteristics of PTFE hollow fiber membranes. Investigated that Increasing Stretching ratio was positive for pore size and porosity but negative for water entry pressure and mechanical property.

5.2 Phase Inversion Method: Phase inversion method is a microporous polymeric membrane fabrication technique in which phase separation of a casting solution takes place in various ways: Non-Solvent-Induced Phase Separation (NIPS), Vapor-Induced Phase Separation (VIPS) or Temperature-Induced Phase Separation (TIPS). These methods are widely used to prepare PP and PVDF-based MD membranes.

Fig 6: Schematic of the four main phase inversion processes (S: Solvent, NS: Non-solvent, H: Heat)

(Eykens et al., 2017)

5.2.1 Non-Solvent-Induced Phase Separation (NIPS): This method is mostly used to fabricate the microporous membrane for commercial reverse osmosis, nanofiltration, ultrafiltration and microfiltration processes. In this method clear homogeneous solution of Polymer and Solvent (dope) cast /formed into desired shape usually flat plate or hollow fiber using suitable support after that immersion in the coagulation bath i.e., nonsolvent bath, nonsolvent must be miscible with the solvent, rapid mass transfer takes place between solvent and nonsolvent lead to phase inversion and formation of microporous solid membrane (Peng et al., 2012)

Khayet & Matsuura (2001) prepared the Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) flat-sheet membranes for MD using Pure water as a pore-forming additive in the casting solution and Dimethylacetamide (DMAC) as the solvent. casting solutions were prepared by adding a PVDF in pure water and DMAC. in this study prepared membranes were characterized in terms of their non wettability, pore size and porosity and investigated that increase in concentration of water in the PVDF casting solution increases the pore size and porosity of the membrane hence decrease the liquid entry Pressure of water (LEP_w).

Feng et al. (2004) fabricated the PVDF membrane with high permeate performance in this study Dimethylacetamide (DMAC) and $LiClO_4 \cdot 3H_2O$ /trimethyl phosphate (TMP) were used as solvent and pore-forming additives. The membrane was prepared by a phase invasion method.

5.2.2 Vapour-Induced Phase Separation (VIPS): In VIPS method the microporous membrane is fabricated by preparing the homogeneous casing solution and film was cast into flat plate or hollow fiber as similar to NIPS method but after casing a film exposure to the vapour phase atmosphere like humid air with high relative humidity. Mass transfer takes place between the solvent from solution and non-solvent from the vapour phase. Film exposure to the vapor phase for a certain time is called exposure time (Fan et al., 2013).

AlMarzooqi et al. (2017) fabricated the Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) for MD by NIPS and VIPS phase inversion method to achieve a porous PVDF membrane with low mass-transfer resistance and high contact angle. Dimethylacetamide (DMAC) and Deionized (DI) water was used as solvent and non-solvent in the NIPS process. VIPS membrane fabrication process is quite similar to NIPS process except that after film casting step film is kept at a humid air atmosphere of relative humidity (RH): 37%, 60% and 80% for a certain time called exposure time. Membranes prepared by the NIPS and VIPS process were characterized and results showed that VIPS membrane Contact angle ($CA \Rightarrow 125^\circ$) was higher than NIPS membrane ($CA=90.74^\circ$). LEP of membranes prepared by both processes, they all range from 103 to 107 kPa which may cause the membrane to become wet. High bubble-point pore size (BP) values for all membranes and LEP increases with thickness.

5.2.3 Thermally induced phase separation (TIPS): This method was first invented by Castro in the late 1970s to prepare the porous PP membrane. In this method homogeneous solution of polymer is prepared by adding polymer into diluent and heating under evacuated temperature. The solution is formed into flat sheet, tube or hollow fiber. After that the phase separation occurs by cooling and quenching, after complete removal of diluent and extractor porous structured membrane is formed (Lloyd et al., 1991).

Lin et al., (2009) fabricated the polypropylene membranes by thermally induced phase separation method using diamyl phthalate (DAP) as a diluent to study the effect of polymer concentration, quenching conditions and coarsening time on membrane morphology and mechanical properties. Investigated that if polymer concentration increases membrane changes from a typical bicontinuous structure to a cellular structure gradually and tensile strength improved well. also observe that quenching into water at higher temperatures larger pore size was obtained. at higher temperature the pore size increases with increase of the coarsening time. Othman et al. (2016) prepared the PP microporous membrane using diphenyl ether (DPE) as a diluent and methanol as an extractor for Separation of reactive Red 3BS from an aqueous solution.

5.2.4 Electrospinning Method: electrospinning is the most established and widely used method for preparation of PVDF porous membrane. In this method polymer dope solution was pumped using a syringe pump in a thin PTFE tube electrical charge by high voltage power supply. the distance between the tip of the sprayers and grounded collector maintained around 12 cm or 15 cm. nanofibers produce from the tip of the sprayers were collected on rotating collector. solvent was evaporated from nascent nanofibers Then a heat-press post-treatment was applied to compress all the nanofibers to form an electro spun membrane (Liao eat al., 2013; Josef & Guterman, 2019).

Fig. 7. Schematic diagram of an electro-spinning setup (Liao eat al., 2013)

6. Characterization of membrane: Membranes applicable for membrane distillation are generally characterized by various performance parameters such as Membrane material, thickness of the membrane, porosity of the membrane, nominal pore size and liquid-entry-pressure of water (Fortunato et al., 2021).

6.1 Membrane Material: Membrane material is one of the most important parameter. Membranes used in MD are generally microporous hydrophobic polymeric membranes. organic compound present in fermentation broths wetted the hydrophobic membrane and reduces the ethanol separation efficiency (Gryta, 2016; Malsuura, 1993).

6.2 Surface morphology: Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is generally used to study the surface morphology of membranes. Surface roughness can be observed by atomic force microscopy (AFM). These techniques are also able to investigate surface porosity, pore size and pore size distribution of prepared membrane. Crystalline structures can be analyzed by X-ray diffractometer (XRD). Zarraa et al. (2024) studied the morphology of produced PVDF membranes using SEM TESCAN (3 XMU, MIRA), presented the SEM imaging of the PVDF membranes as shown in Fig 8 and 9. The average pore size of PVDF membrane was observed i.e 0.22 μm .

Fig 8. SEM of PVDF membrane (Zarraa et al., 2024)

Fig 9. SEM of PVDF membrane (Zarraa et al., 2024)

Mohammad et al. (2015) characterized the PTFE membrane by AFM to determine the surface topography, pore structure and dimension and pore size distribution. reported results showed that 45% of pore sizes are in the range of 0.2 to 0.3 mm. also investigated that the membrane surface is not smooth by capturing the 3-D AFM image as shown in Fig 10.

Fig. 10. 3-D image of the PTFE membrane and morphology observation via nodules (brighter) and pores (darker) (Mohammad et al., 2015).

Himma et al. (2017) studied the surface morphology of prepared Superhydrophobic Polypropylene membrane using Scanning electronic microscopy (SEM, JEOL-JSM-6510LV, JEOL Ltd, Japan).

In the research article Preparation and characterization of PTFE flat sheet membrane to study the Effect of sodium benzoate content Ghani et al. (2017) characterized the membrane by XRD to study the crystalline structure of PTFE membrane. XRD results (Fig 11) presented in this article showed that Increasing sodium benzoate content was positive for pore size and porosity but crystallinity mechanical properties decreased.

Fig 11 XRD patterns for PTFE1, PTFE2 and PTFE3 (Ghani et al., 2017)

6.3 Liquid Entry Pressure: Liquid entry Pressure is measured to investigate the membrane wetting. LEP_w is pressure applied to pure water from the feed side until the water penetrates into the membrane. Smolders & Franken, (1989) described the procedure to determine the LEP of hydrophobic membranes. LEP can also calculated by using the Cantor–Laplace equation

$$LEP = \frac{-2Y\cos\theta}{r_{max}} \dots\dots Eq.4$$

where Y is the surface tension of the wetting liquid (For water at 25 C, 0.07199 N/m), θ is the contact angle between the membrane and the wetting liquid (water) and r_{max} is the maximum pore radius of the membrane (i.e., bubble-point pore size) (Fan et al., 2013).

Gostoli & Sarti (1989) determined the minimum entry pressure for water in PTFE hydrophobic membrane and found it to be nearly 2.7 bars; on the other hand. They also observed that for ethanol water solution LEP decreases with increasing ethanol concentration in the solution and finally vanishes at 75wt.%.

6.4 Membrane Thickness: Membrane thickness is a parameter that may control the mechanical strength, permeate flux, LEP and surface properties like BP and CA. If the membrane is sufficiently thick LEP increases and less pore is formed on the surface hence contact angle (CA) decreases.

AlMarzooqi et al. (2017) fabricated the Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) and investigated that the casting thickness played a significant role in maintaining a small BP. BP size sufficiently increases with decreasing casting thickness hence contact angle decreases also the LEP decreases with decreasing Casting thickness.

6.5 Porosity of the membrane: Porosity of membrane is the ratio of volume of pore to the volume of membrane, the porosity of microporous polymeric membrane can be measured by immersing the Polymeric membrane in i-butanol/isopropanol for 24 hrs after that taken out the membrane and weigh to calculate the porosity. The following equation can be used to determine the porosity of the membrane.

$$A_k = \frac{(W_2 - W_1)\rho_1}{\rho_1 W_2 + (\rho_2 - \rho_1)W_1} \times 100\% \dots\dots Eq. 5$$

where W_1 and W_2 is the initial membrane weight and immersed membrane weight, ρ_1 and ρ_2 the density of PVDF, and i-butanol/isopropanol (Gu et al., 2006).

Another method was also reported by Smolders & Franker (1989) to determine the porosity of polymeric hydrophobic microporous membrane.

Ghani et al. (2017) prepared the PTFE flat sheet membranes and Pore size distributions was determined by using mercury intrusion porosimeter Auto pore V, Micromeritics Instrument Corp. (USA). They observed that the porosity of the PTFE flat sheet membrane is in the range of 36.41% to 74.32% with average pore diameter is in the range of 74.8 nm to 1068.4 nm.

6.6 IPA bubble point: IPA (isopropyl alcohol) bubble point method is able to determine the maximum pore size and the pore size distribution. In this method the porosity of the membrane can be calculated by calculating the density of the polymer material and density of the membrane using a pycnometer, balance, isopropyl alcohol (IPA) and water (Khayat & Matsuura, 2001). Detailed procedure for calculating the pore size using IPA is given in article (Smolders & Franker, 1989).

6.7 Maximum pore size: Maximum pore size is the opening in the membrane denoted by pore diameter or pore radius. It is determined by following equation:

$$\text{Pore size} = \frac{4B\gamma}{p} \dots\dots\dots\text{Eq. 6}$$

where B is the pore size morphology constant, γ is the surface tension of IPA, p is the bubble point pressure in which value of B is 1 for circular pore and >1 for an elliptical or irregularly shaped pore (Smolders & Franker, 1989).

6.8 Contact angle: Contact angle is one of the methods used to measure the hydrophobicity of the produced membranes. The contact angles meter is an instrument used to measure the contact angle. Huang et al. (2011) were prepared the PTFE/PVA composite films and contact angle measurement test were carried on contact angle meter (Jinshengxin Inspection instrument Co., Ltd., model JYSP-180) at 25 °C with 40–50% relative humidity. Obtained result shown that contact angle was 139.81° for PTFE/PVA mass ratios 4:1 and 121.00° for PTFE/PVA mass ratios 1:1. In the review research work of Baghel et al. (2017) suggested the young's equation to calculate the contact angle as follows:

$$\text{Cos}\theta = \frac{\gamma_{SA} - \gamma_{SL}}{\gamma_{LA}} \dots\dots\dots\text{Eq. 7}$$

where γ_{SA} and γ_{SL} is the surface tension coefficient of the solid-air interface and solid-liquid, similarly γ_{LA} is the surface tension coefficient of the liquid-air interface. if the contact angle between $0^\circ < \theta < 45^\circ$ membranes is highly hydrophilic, if the contact angle between $90^\circ < \theta < 180^\circ$ membranes is highly hydrophobic.

7. Membrane Performance

7.1 Permeation flux: Permeation flux is performance characteristics of the membrane, defined as volume of ethanol collected per unit active surface area of membrane and unit time. It is calculated by the following equation.

$$J = \frac{V}{A \times t} \dots\dots\dots\text{Eq. 8}$$

where J is the permeation flux in (volume/m² h) V is the permeated ethanol volume in litre (L), A is the effective membrane area in m² and t is the time in h (Jia et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2013).

7.2 Concentration factor, CF: Concentration factor CF is the degree of increasing concentration of the component in the membrane operation. According to Smolders & Franker (1989) In the membrane distillation process, it is the ratio of concentration of retentate (C_r) to the concentration of feed (C_f) for the dilute system, retentate feed is continuously circulated to achieve a desired concentration feed. it is calculated by

$$CF=C_r/C_f \dots\dots\dots Eq. 9$$

7.3 The separation factors: Separation factor is also the performance characteristic of membrane and it is calculated on a molar basis as (Gostoli & Sarti, 1989).

$$\alpha = \frac{1-x_2}{x_2} \frac{x_1}{1-x_1} \dots\dots\dots Eq. 10$$

where x_1 and x_2 are the mole fraction of ethanol in feed and distillate respectively.

8. Process Characteristics:

Performance of the membrane distillation depends on many process characteristics like (i) feed temperature, (ii) feed concentration, (iii) membrane type, and (iv) feed flow rate,

8.1 Ethanol concentration: Ethanol concentration is one of the parameter which affect the MD performance. If the ethanol concentration in the feed is higher there is a possibility of membrane wetting also the penetration pressure reduces hence the membrane loses its hydrophobicity and the MD process becomes water selective. If the ethanol content is low the process becomes ethanol selective. The separation factor also changes with change in feed composition at higher concentration it will move towards the unit and separation depends on the temperature (Gostoli & Sarti, 1989).

8.2 Feed temperature: Feed temperature is also an important parameter for MD processes which affects both permeate flux and total energy requirement. Many researchers have reported that as the feed temperature increases the permeate flux also increases due to increase in vapour pressure of ethanol and water (Nassif et al., 2022).

Gostoli & Sarti (1989) studied the separation of ethanol water mixture by membrane distillation using porous flat PTFE membrane. They pointed out that the increase in temperature difference between the evaporation and the condensation surfaces separation factor also increases i.e., sufficient temperature difference is required to obtain a remarkable separation factor. also investigated that in AGMD separation factor changes with change in gas phase due to change in the temperature difference between the evaporation and condensation surfaces.

8.3. Feed flow rate: Feed flow rate is also an important process characteristic which affects the performance of membrane distillation. Gryta (2013) studied the effect of feed flow rate on ethanol separation in the membrane distillation process. obtained results show that feed flow rate increases the turbulence, reduces the ethanol concentration near the membrane and affects the ethanol separation. An optimal feed flow rate with good turbulence can enhance the efficiency of the ethanol separation process.

9. Conclusion: Considering the Increasing fuel demand of the transportation sector many countries including India are focusing on bioethanol as an alternative fuel. Ethanol is a biofuel produced by the fermentation of the biomass using yeasts. In the fermentation process continuous ethanol removal is important because increasing product concentration hampers the microbial activity by product inhibition. integration of membrane distillation with the fermentation process is a promising technique for removal of ethanol from fermentation broths. Membrane distillation is a technique widely used in combination of various separation and purification processes using commercial microporous PTFE, PVDF and PP membrane. membrane distillation with attractive configuration provides effective operating conditions for the separation of ethanol from fermentation broths. This review research focused on various membrane configuration, membrane materials used in MD, their characterization and effect of process characteristics on the performance of membrane.

DCMD configuration is simplest, cost effective and easy to operate, driving force for membrane distillation is vapour pressure difference induced by the temperature difference across the membrane. The temperature difference in the DCMD is quite small because of the liquid phase present in the permeate side. In AGMD temperature difference may increase with increasing air gap hence the separation factor is improved. In VMD vacuum is applied in the permeate side hence permeation flux is improved with high rejection rate. In SGMD, permeated vapour molecules are swept by cold inert gas blowing through the permeate side. In this configuration increasing sweeping gas flow rate increases permeation flux but selectivity decreases, also the operating cost is quite high because external condenser is required to reduce the temperature of sweeping gas.

PTFE, PVDF and PP polymeric materials are widely used to prepare the membrane for membrane distillation. PTFE has excellent hydrophobicity as compared to PVDF and PP but fabrication is very difficult and costly due to insolubility in almost all solvent hence modification with PTFE is quite difficult. On the other hand, Preparation of PVDF and PP membranes are very easy and economical and can be prepared by solution casting and phase inversion method because of their solubility with many solvents hence membrane surface can be easily modified due to adding and blending other material/polymer.

Permeation flux and separation factor are the performance parameters which depend on membrane characteristics and operating characteristics. For the separation of ethanol from fermentation broth using membrane distillation mostly depends on membrane material, membrane pore size, membrane thickness, feed flow rate, ethanol concentration and feed temperature many researchers obtained remarkable permeation flux and separation factor by optimizing these parameters but still improvement needed. modification in membrane material and change in fabrication method can improve the performance of membrane.

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